

Slope consolidation in vineyards through adapting agronomical practices

SPOKE 6 – PRIMARY AGROINDUSTRY

DELIVERABLE D7.2

Version history

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Glossary

Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will [redacted] for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will [redacted] their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will [redacted] for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated [redacted] Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will [redacted] for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will [redacted] for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be [redacted] by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports the method, and the analyses performed to identify the effects of different land uses and agricultural managements on shallow slope stability of cultivated sloping terrains. The analyses have been carried out in Oltrepò Pavese area, across different geological and geomorphological settings. The quantitative contribution to slope stability of different land managements have been integrated with the assessment of this parameter for a suppletive crop (olive trees) to grapevines, in order to estimate the effect of this land use to shallow slope stability compared with the most traditional land managements (vineyards, sowed fields, shrublands, woodlands) present in the study area. This deliverable shows the preliminary results of these analyses, which will allow ultimately to reducing risk costs towards slope instabilities and to improve land use management.

A. QUANTITATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE CONTRIBUTION OF DIFFERENT LAND USES TO SLOPE STABILITY

Materials and methods

The contribution of different land uses to shallow slope stability was estimated for the mainland uses present in Oltrepò Pavese area. The results of this property, shown in Bordoni et al. (2020) for vineyards with different managements, sowed fields, shrublands and woodlands, were integrated with new measured values referred to another suppletive crop to grapevines in the study area, namely the olive trees.

This contribution was measured in different test-sites with the presence of olive trees (Table 1), representative of the main geological and geomorphological settings of the study area and with different age of the plants.

The contribution of the considered land uses to slope stability was quantified by means of the quantification of the root mechanical reinforcement (c_r). This reinforcement is made mostly by small roots of the shallow soil horizons, particularly in the first 2 m from ground, which mobilize their tensile strength by soil-root interaction increasing the compound matrix strength (Wu, 2012; Cohen and Schwarz 2017). c_r was estimated applying Root Bundle Model (RBM; Cohen et al., 2011). The adopted procedure implemented also a survival Weibull function for considering the potential variability of the root properties, according to the Schwarz et al. (2013)'s approach called Root Bundle Model-Weibull (RBMw).

Root system architecture and root mechanical properties were required for the application of this model. In particular, the root system architecture was considered taking into account the number of roots per m^2 of soil, measured in trench pits in each test-site, as root density, and the

power law relationship between the root length (L , in mm) and the root diameter (D , in mm), measured in correspondence of each test site (Eq. 1), too:

$$L = L_0(D)^\sigma \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

, where L_0 is a multiplicative coefficient and σ is an exponential coefficient.

Table 1: Main features of the test-sites where the root reinforcement of olive trees were measured

Test site	Slope altitude m s.l.m.	Slope angle °	Slope aspect	Soil texture	Age of the trees yr	Type
FNG1	342	9	S	Silt with clay	12	Olive yard
FNG2	338	8	S	Silt with clay	12	Olive yard
BNC	309	21	S	Clayey silt	>50	Single olive trees
BLB1	219	2	NW	Clayey silt	25	Olive yard
BLB2	216	5	NW	Clayey silt	25	Olive yard
LUZ	164	10	W	Clayey silt	20	Olive yard
COLOMB	370	15	W	Silt with clay	15	Olive yard
CASA1	305	20	SW	Clayey sandy silt	17	Olive yard
CASA2	296	19	SW	Clayey sandy silt	22	Olive yard
SNG	242	15	SW	Clayey sandy silt	>50	Single olive trees
FDN1	218	23	S	Clayey silt	10	Olive yard
FDN2	192	22	S	Clayey sandy silt	8	Olive yard

Root mechanical properties were measured since roots collected in each test site from the trench. Tensile tests were, then, performed for each root according to the approach proposed by Bischetti et al. (2009). This method allowed to measure the tensile force and its trend during an increase of the applied stresses, at a strain rate of 10 mm/min. The tensile force was measured by a load cell (full scale of 500 N, accuracy of 0.5 N), while the diameter of each root was estimated as the average of three values taken at three points of the root by a caliper.

The results of these tests were represented as power-law relations, the former relating the tensile force at rupture (F_{max} , in N) with the diameter (D , in mm) (Eq. 2), the latter relating Young's modulus (E , in MPa) with the diameter (D , in mm) (Eq. 3):

$$F_{max} = F_0(D)^\xi \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$E = E_0(D)^\beta \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

, where F_0 and E_0 are multiplicative coefficients, and ξ and β are exponential coefficients.

Root system architecture and mechanical properties, were then combined for a set of roots, to calculate c_r as the sum of the contribution made by each single root (F) multiplied by the Weibull survival function (S), for all the roots present in a certain soil profile, in correspondence of a particular soil level (Eq. 4):

$$c_r = \sum_{i=1}^n F(D_i, \Delta x) S(\Delta x^*) \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

, where (Eq. 5):

$$F(D_i, \Delta x) = \frac{\pi E_0}{4L_0} D_i^{2+\beta+\sigma} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where, Δx is the estimated displacement, Δx^* is the normalized estimated displacement, as the ratio between the displacement measured by each single tensile test and the corresponding values of displacement obtained using the fitted values of tensile forces, S was calculated according to Eq. (6):

$$S(\Delta x^*) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{\Delta x^*}{\lambda}\right)^\omega\right) \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

, where λ is the scale Weibull parameter and ω is the Weibull parameter.

c_r was quantified at some depths (0.3, 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5 m from ground) for analysing its evolution along a soil profile. c_r of the tested olive trees were compared with the range of values obtained in Bordoni et al. (2020) for the other land uses considered in the study area: vineyards with total tillage (VN-TT); vineyards with tillage (VN-TIL); vineyards with permanent grass cover (VN-PGC); alternating vineyards (VN-ALT); sowed areas (SA); shrublands (UNC); woodlands (WOOD).

Results

The results of the measure of root reinforcement are provided in Table 2.

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of root reinforcements in the analysed olive trees classes, compared with other land uses in the study area. OLIVE<20 years) olive trees of less than 20 years; OLIVE 20-50 years) olive trees with age between 20 and 50 years; OLIVE>50 years) olive trees of more than 50 years; VN-TT) vineyards with total tillage; VN-TIL) vineyards with tillage; VN-PGC) vineyards with permanent grass cover; VN-ALT) alternating vineyards; SA) sowed areas; UNC) shrublands; woodlands (WOOD).

Land use	c_r at 0.3 m from ground kPa	c_r at 0.5 m from ground kPa	c_r at 1.0 m from ground kPa	c_r at 1.5 m from ground kPa
OLIVE<20 years	2.14±0.84	2.76±0.99	2.03±0.71	1.48±0.59
OLIVE 20-50 years	4.69±2.22	4.71±1.55	3.41±0.98	2.23±0.63
OLIVE>50 years	4.98±0.30	5.29±0.35	4.32±0.23	3.49±0.35
VN-TT	0.58±0.24	1.69±0.50	0.99±0.29	0.60±0.18
VN-TIL	3.21±0.57	3.97±1.10	2.18±1.01	1.31±0.53
VN-ALT	11.73±2.34	14.28±2.59	9.18±1.99	5.56±1.59
VN-PGC	6.53±1.59	8.58±2.29	4.80±1.41	3.22±0.85
SA	1.81±0.77	1.63±0.23	0.91±0.30	0.46±0.14
UNC	1.20±0.53	2.00±0.26	0.74±0.30	0.36±0.06
WOOD	10.73±1.43	14.92±2.60	8.56±3.80	5.93±2.09

B. PROBABILITY OF FAILURE FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

Materials and methods

Lu and Godt (2008)'s model was adopted to calculate the shallow slope stability in correspondence of different land uses, by the calculation of the slope safety factor FS taking into account hydrological properties influencing shallow slope stability, where also root mechanical reinforcement can be inserted within the component of soil cohesion (Eq. 7):

$$FS = \frac{\tan\phi'}{\tan\theta} + \frac{2(c'+c_r)}{\gamma Z \sin 2\theta} - \frac{\sigma^s}{\gamma Z} ((\tan\theta + \cot\theta)\tan\phi') \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

,where ϕ' is the soil friction angle, θ is the slope angle, c' is the soil effective cohesion, c_r is the root mechanical reinforcement, γ is the soil unit weight, Z is the depth below ground level where the potential sliding surface could form, σ^s is the suction stress, allowing to represent the mechanical behavior and the state of stress of a soil according to its hydrological conditions in terms of saturation degree and pore water pressure (Lu and Godt, 2013).

For overcoming the limitation of this deterministic approach, Eq. 7 was applied considering a probabilistic approach based on a Monte Carlo procedure, run for a total of 1000 repetitions, each considering randomly selected values for each variable (ϕ' , c' , c_r , γ , σ^s). ϕ' , c' , c_r and γ were extracted for these scenarios from a normal distribution, while σ^s values were taken from a uniform distribution between 0 and 10 kPa. Furthermore, the model was applied for the typical slope steepness of the study area ($>5^\circ$), and keeping soil depth of 1 m, which corresponds to the typical depth of shallow landslides sliding surfaces in the study area (Bordoni et al., 2020).

The number of times in which calculated FS was less than 1 (conditions of instability) was divided for the total number of repetitions that FS was quantified (1000 times), obtaining the failure probability (Pr) as (Eq. 8):

$$Pr = P(FS < 1) \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

Pr for different slope angles was quantified for all the land uses of the study area considering c_r ranges of each land use present in Table 2 and was calculated for the two most widespread soil types of Oltrepò Pavese: i) clayey silts or clayey-sandy silts; ii) clays with silts, silts with clays or silty clays. Table 3 shows the mean and the standard deviation of the geotechnical properties (ϕ' , c' , γ) used for the computation of the Pr for both the soil types.

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of the geotechnical parameters used for the assessment of the failure probability for both the considered soil types. ϕ') soil friction angle; c') soil cohesion; γ) soil unit weight.

Soil type	ϕ'	c'	γ
	°	kPa	kN/m ³
Clayey silts or clayey-sandy silts	26±4	1.8±1.6	18.0±0.8

Clays with silts, silts with clays or silty clays	12±4	0.0±0.0	19.4±0.5
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Results

The slope stability analyses, performed through the probabilistic approach, highlighted the significant role of different types of land uses on the proneness of a hillslope towards shallow slope failures, for both soil types (Figs. 1, 2).

Figure 1: Failure probability (Pr), as a function of slope steepness, for different land uses, considering clayey silts/clayey-sandy silts soils

Figure 2: Failure probability (Pr), as a function of slope steepness, for different land uses, considering clays with silts/silty clays

References

- Bischetti, G.B., Chiaradia, E., Epis, T., Morlotti, E. 2009. Root cohesion of forest species in the Italian Alps. *Plant Soil* 324, 71–89.
- Bordoni, M., Cislighi, A., Vercesi, A., Bischetti, G.B., Meisina, C., 2020. Effects of plant roots on soil shear strength and shallow landslide proneness in an area of northern Italian Apennines. *Bull. Eng. Geol. Environ.* 79, 3361-3381.
- Cohen, D., Schwarz, M., Or, D., 2011. An analytical fiber bundle model for pullout mechanics of root bundles. *J. Geophys. Res.* 116, F03010.
- Cohen, D., Schwarz, M., 2017. Tree-root control of shallow landslides. *Earth Surf. Dynam.* 5, 451–477.
- Lu, N., Godt, J.W., 2008. Infinite slope stability under steady unsaturated seepage conditions. *Water Resour. Res.* 44, W11404.
- Lu, N., Godt, J.W., 2013. *Hillslope hydrology and stability*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Schwarz, M., Giadrossich, F., Cohen, D., 2013. Modeling root reinforcement using a root failure Weibull survival function. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 17, 4367–4377.
- Wu, T.H., 2012. Root reinforcement of soil: review of analytical models, test results and application to design. *Can. Geotech. J.* 50, 259–274.